

A study on teachers' level of commitment to their profession

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Abstract

This study investigates teachers' commitment to their profession in relation to various factors. The research utilized a survey model, employing convenience sampling to collect data. The study group comprised 245 teachers from public schools in the Ermenek district of Karaman province. A personal information form was utilized to gather demographic details, including gender, subject area, faculty of graduation, type of school, place of residence, year of entering the profession, and mentorship status. The "Teacher Commitment to Profession Scale," consisting of three sub-dimensions (commitment to the profession, commitment to students, and dedicated work), was employed to assess the level of commitment. Quantitative statistical analysis was conducted using the SPSS 25 package, employing one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and t-tests. The findings indicate that the level of commitment to the teaching profession does not vary significantly based on gender, subject area, place of residence, type of school, years of professional experience, or having a mentor teacher. This holds true for the sub-dimensions of commitment to the profession, commitment to students, dedicated work, and the overall scale score (commitment to the profession). Based on the study results, it is recommended that further research be undertaken in different educational institutions and with diverse samples to enhance the generalizability of findings.

Keywords: Commitment, Commitment to Profession, Teaching Profession, Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Education is the foundation for participation in the highly competitive global economy of the 21st century, based on technological change, communication and knowledge transfer, as well as major changes in the production, transportation, distribution and economic value of information. In other words, education is the fulcrum of the socio-political and economic development of our time (Lawal, 2012). The main goal of education systems is to develop the qualified manpower of that country and to ensure that its citizens receive civic education. In order to realize this, each education system defines a model of human educator within the framework of its own educational philosophy and workforce policy and organizes its educational activities accordingly (Karagözoğlu, 2003). Education offers many opportunities such as ensuring socialization by transferring existing values to the younger generation, supporting individuals to shape their personality by helping them discover and develop their personal talents, and helping individuals to perform their profession by gaining the knowledge, skills and behaviors they need to survive and contribute to social life. The ability of education systems to fully fulfill these basic tasks is equivalent to the quality of the teachers in the system (MEB, 2017). It is teachers who play a leading role in the social, political and economic development of countries, in the formation of a qualified workforce, in the creation of an environment of peace and social tranquility in society, in individuals leading a more social life, in equipping social life, and in the transmission of cultures and values. Teachers are the true architects of society and artisans of human personality (Eskicumalı, 2002).

When considered as a profession, teaching is a profession that forms the basis for preparing individuals for all other professions (Barwal, 2011). The teaching profession is the art of raising the individual or generation to be raised as good, useful, beneficial citizens who always help the family, the environment, the nation, the state and the country, and these individuals raised by those who continue their profession as teachers will make the family and the country happy, develop the homeland and strengthen the nation. In this respect, the future status and economic development of our country and state depend first and foremost on the professional success of teachers (Tekişik, 1986). Because the quality of a nation is measured by the quality of its citizens. The quality of citizens is closely linked to the quality of the education system, and the quality of education is closely linked

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to the joint efforts of educators, planners and administration. What is important here is the quality of teachers (Parvez & Shakir, 2013). Because individuals, who continue their lives together in the society, gain the values, knowledge and skills required to comply with the rules of the society, to respond to its values and expectations, and to interact socially with their environment through the education of school teachers (Bozdaş, 2013).

When educational organizations are considered from an institutional perspective, it is seen that teachers play an important role. This is because teachers are at the forefront of educational institutions that ensure an increase in the quality of individuals. In these institutions where students are the target audience, teachers are the ones who interact in order to realize instructional goals. In this context, the success of teachers in their work is also directly related to the success of educational institutions (Turhan, Demirli, & Nazik, 2012). At this point, the important factor is the level of teachers' commitment to their profession.

Commitment to the profession is a strong disposition for teaching and learning (McGovern & Miller, 2008). When dedicated teachers share the beauty of their field with their students, they reflect a strong desire for their profession through behaviors that support student learning (Fried, 2001). Teachers' professional commitment can be determined by criteria such as adopting teaching as a profession, being proud of their profession, seeing the value of the teaching profession as superior to other professions, being aware that teaching is an ideal profession for professional life and accepting that it is a good career, being recognized in the teaching profession, and continuing the teaching profession even if they do not need to work economically (Celep, 1998). Commitment to the profession is realized through voluntary, self-sacrificing work, focusing on tasks that are appropriate to the requirements of the profession (Saribaş, Akça, & Meydan, 2020). Celep (2000) defines the concept of professional commitment as the employee's adoption of the necessary roles and behaviors as well as his/her attitude towards the profession, taking into account the defined goals and values of the profession, and showing an effective working attitude. According to Malak Akdağ (2020), age, time spent in the profession, education level, being male or female and nationality are among the personal factors affecting the level of commitment. In addition to these, working environment and environmental conditions (Aydemir & Endirlik, 2019); self-efficacy, self-confidence and goodwill can be listed among the factors affecting professional commitment (Özkalp & Meydan, 2015).

In the literature on teachers' professional commitment; the relationship between 21st century teacher skills and professional commitment of individuals who continue their profession as teachers (Kozikoğlu & Özcanlı, 2020), the relationship between organizational trust and professional commitment of teachers working in basic education institutions (Altunay, 2020). century teacher skills and professional commitment (Kozikoğlu & Özcanlı, 2020), the relationship between organizational trust and professional commitment of teachers working in basic education institutions (Altunay,

2017), professional commitment of preschool teachers (Başaran & Bozyer, 2019), paid teachers' commitment to the profession (Saribaş, Akça, & Meydan, 2020), and the relationship between commitment to the profession, empathy levels and love for children of educators working with students with autism (Sarıkaya & Özdemir, 2017). In a study investigating teachers' thoughts about their commitment to their profession, it was observed that teachers loved their profession very much and that commitment to the profession was listed in the categories of (1) excessive love for the profession, (2) spending more time, (3) focusing more on students, (4) having knowledge and development in the professional field, (5) communication with school stakeholders, and (6) transferring the knowledge and values acquired to the other party (Croswell, 2006). In Saracaloğlu, Örer, and Sivaci's (2018) study, it was seen that although teachers love their profession, they experience burnout in their profession due to reasons such as excessive workload, gradual deterioration of student level, crowded classes, parent attitude, attitude and behavior of the administration towards teachers, developments in education policies and loss of reputation of the teaching profession. In Kozikoğlu's (2016) study, it was found that the professional commitment of new teachers was high, and in Bozdaş's (2013) study, it was found that classroom and branch teachers' commitment to their profession was low, and that teachers' commitment to their profession was at medium and low levels. In addition, there are studies (Keskin, 2005; Pehlivan-Kapan, 2020) examining the effects of teachers' professional commitment on student achievement in the literature.

When the literature is examined, it is seen that many studies have been conducted on teachers' professional commitment and it is stated that teachers with high professional commitment show more success in their fields and this success positively affects the learning-teaching process. In addition, high professional commitment is an important concept in achieving the goals of education. Especially in the realization of the goals to be achieved in education and training, it is of particular importance to investigate teachers' commitment to their profession. In this context, the general purpose of the research is to examine the teachers' commitment to the teaching profession according to some demographic variables (gender, place of residence, type of graduation faculty, school level/type and having a guidance counselor in the first year of the profession). The questions created for this general purpose in the research are listed as follows

1. What is the level of teachers' commitment to the teaching profession?
2. Teachers' level of commitment to the teaching profession;
 - Gender,
 - The settlement where they work,
 - Type of faculty graduated from,
 - The level/type of school in which they work,

- Do they show significant differences according to the status of having a counselor/guidance counselor in the first year they started their profession?

METHOD

Since the aim of this study is to reveal teachers' commitment to their profession according to various demographic variables, the research was conducted with the general survey model, which is one of the quantitative research methods. The general survey model is survey research conducted with the whole universe or a group, sample or sample to be taken from the universe with the aim of reaching a general opinion about the universe in a universe consisting of a large number of more elements (Karasar, 2016).

Study group

The study group consists of 245 teachers working in schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in the 1st semester of the 2019-2020 academic year and reached by convenience sampling method. Personal information about the study group is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of the Teachers in the Study Group by Gender

Number participants on the basis of			
Variables	Groups	F	%
Gender	Male	122	49.8
	Female	122	49.8
	Missing Data	1	0.04

The data in Table 1 show the distribution of teachers according to gender. Table 1 shows that 49.8% of the teachers were male, 49.8% were female and 0.4% were missing data.

The data in Table 2 shows the distribution of teachers by course/lessons. According to these data, it is seen that the highest percentage of the teachers in the study group is in classroom teaching with 11%, then English with 10,6%, and the lowest percentage is in health services, justice and accommodation with 0,4%.

Table 3: Distribution of the Teachers in the Study Group According to the Faculty of Graduation

Number participants on the basis of			
Variables	Groups	F	%
Faculty of Graduation	Faculty of Education	155	63.3
	Other Faculties	76	31
	Missing Data	14	5.7

Table 3 shows that 63.3% of the teachers are graduates of the Faculty of Education, 31% are graduates of other faculties and 5.7% are missing data.

Table 2: Distribution of the Teachers in the Study Group by Gender Distribution of Teachers in the Study Group According to Course/Lessons

Number participants on the basis of			
Variables	Groups	F	%
Course /Lesson	Turkish	16	6.5
	Science	12	4.9
	English	26	10.6
	Secondary Mathematics	6	2.4
	Physics	4	1.6
	Elementary Mathematics	18	4.3
	Social Studies	12	4.9
	Physical Education and Sports	17	6.9
	Religious Culture and Ethics	10	4.1
	Turkish Language and Literature	18	7.3
	Technology Design	4	1.6
	Special Education	5	2
	Chemistry	3	1.2
	Music	6	2.4
	Philosophy Group	2	0.8
	Guidance	9	3.7
	Geography	5	2
	Biology	6	2.4
	Information Technologies	8	3.3
	Preschool	9	3.7
	Classroom Teaching	27	11
	History	5	2
	Health Services	1	0.4
	Imam Hatip High School Vocational Courses	3	1.2
Accounting and Finance	2	0.8	
German	2	0.8	
Justice	1	0.4	
Accommodation	1	0.4	
Visual Arts	2	0.8	
Missing Data	5	0.2	

Table 4 shows the distribution of teachers according to the type of school they work in. According to this distribution, 48.1% of the teachers work in secondary schools, 12.2% in primary schools, 16.7% in Anatolian high schools, 11% in vocational technical high schools, 4.1% in science high schools, 4.1% in imam hatip high schools and the remaining 3.3% in other schools and 0.8% is missing data.

Table 4: Distribution of the Teachers in the Study Group by Gender

Number participants on the basis of			
Variables	Groups	F	%
Type of School	Primary School	30	12.2
	Middle School	117	48.1
	Anatolian High School	41	16.7
	Science High School	10	4.1
	Vocational Technical High School	27	11
	Religious High School	10	4.1
	Other	8	3.3

According to the data in Table 5, it is seen that the distribution of teachers by settlement is 72.3% in the district, 19.2% in the city center and 8.3% in the village.

Table 5: Distribution of the Teachers in the Study Group According to the Place of Work

Number participants on the basis of			
Variables	Groups	F	%
Place of Work Province	Province	47	19.2
	District	175	72.3
	Village	20	8.3
	Missing Data	3	1.2

Table 6 shows that 65.3% of the teachers had a guidance counselor/mentor at the beginning of their career, 31.4% did not have one, and the remaining 3.3% is missing data.

Table 6: Distribution According to the Status of Counselor/Reader Teacher in the Study Group

Number participants on the basis of			
Variables	Groups	F	%
Status of Counselor/Reader Teacher	Yes	160	65.3
	No	77	3.4
	Missing Data	8	3.3

Data Collection Tools

In the study, "Personal Information Form" was used to collect demographic information about the teachers. The personal information form was used to collect information about gender, branch, faculty of graduation, place of employment, type of school, and the status of being a counselor/mentor teacher in the year they started teaching.

The "Commitment to Teaching Profession Scale", which was used to determine teachers' commitment to the teaching profession and whose validity and reliability was conducted by Kozikoğlu and Senemoğlu (2018), is a 20-item Likert-type five-point rating scale. The minimum score that can be obtained

from the scale is 25 and the maximum score is 100. High scores indicate that teachers are dedicated to the teaching profession. According to the results of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted to test the validity of the scale, a scale with three sub-factors consisting of 20 items and explaining 58.27% of the total variance emerged. The first factor was named "Commitment to Profession", the second factor was named "Commitment to Students" and the third factor was named "Selfless Work". Commitment to the Profession indicates that the teacher loves his/her profession, is proud of his/her profession and wants to continue his/her profession with a sense of belonging to the profession. Commitment to Students indicates that the teacher does everything possible for the development of the students without the concept of time and space and uses all the opportunities for the students. Selfless Work indicates that the teacher makes a lot of effort to improve himself/herself professionally and is aware of the developments in his/her field. In order to determine the reliability of the scale, Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient was calculated and the results were 0.92 for the first factor, 0.86 for the second factor, 0.70 for the third factor and 0.90 for the total scale, and according to these values, the scale was found to be reliable. As a result of the item analysis conducted to determine the discrimination levels of the items in the scale, it was concluded that the item-scale correlations varied between 0.387 and 0.769, and the t-test result regarding the difference between the upper and lower group of 27% was significant. According to these data, it can be said that the scale items are discriminative.

In this study, the Cronbach Alpha (α) internal consistency coefficient for the overall scale was calculated as $\alpha=.93$. In the reliability analysis results for the sub-dimensions of the scale, $\alpha=.91$ for the first sub-dimension, commitment to the profession, $\alpha=.77$ for the second sub-dimension, commitment to students, and $\alpha=.90$ for the third sub-dimension, selfless work.

Data analysis

The data of the study were analyzed using independent sample t-test and one-way analysis of variance (One Way ANOVA). The t-test, which is used to determine whether the difference between the averages of two unrelated samples is significant, was used to determine whether the teachers' commitment to the profession differs according to the gender variable, whether they had a guide/counselor in the first year of their profession, and whether they graduated from the faculty of education and other faculties. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test whether the differences between the averages of unrelated or more samples were significant and to determine whether teachers' commitment to their profession differed significantly according to the type and location of the school where they worked.

RESULTS

In this part of the study, the findings obtained as a result of the analysis of the data obtained with the scale of commitment to teaching profession are presented and interpreted in tabular form.

Table 7: Teachers' Level of Commitment to Profession

Scale	Sub Dimensions	Mean (\bar{X})	SD
Commitment to the Profession	Commitment to Profession	4.35	.520
	Commitment to Students	4.37	.643
	Selfless Work	4.20	.592
Total		4.40	.561

Teachers' level of commitment to profession

When table 7 is examined, it is seen that teachers' level of commitment to the profession (\bar{X} =4.40) is at a high level. When the sub-dimensions of the scale are considered separately, it is seen that there is a sub-dimension of commitment to the profession (\bar{X} =4.35), a sub-dimension of commitment to students (\bar{X} =4.37) and a sub-dimension of selfless work (\bar{X} =4.20), and according to these values, it is concluded that their level of commitment is high in the sub-dimensions of the scale.

Comparison of commitment to teaching profession according to gender

The results of the independent samples t-test analysis to determine whether there is a significant difference in the teachers' commitment to teaching profession scale and its sub-dimensions according to gender variable are presented in Table 8.

When the values in table 8 are examined, the results of the independent samples t-test conducted to compare the professional commitment of male and female teachers show that there are no statistically significant differences in terms of professional commitment of male and female teachers ($t(242) = 1.569$; $p > 0.05$). This shows that male and female teachers have similar levels of professional commitment.

When the results of the sub-dimensions of the scale are examined, it is seen that the mean scores of the sub-dimensions of commitment to profession ($t(242) = 1.248$; $p > 0.05$), commitment to students ($t(242) = 1.016$; $p > 0.05$) and selfless work ($t(242) = 1.658$; $p > 0.05$) do not create a significant difference according to gender.

It was found that 8% of the respondents thought the study environment at Nepalese universities was poor, 35% thought it was fair, 48% thought it was good and 8% thought it was very good. The respondents also gave their opinions regarding the educational cost in the higher education. 42% of the respondents thought educational cost were reasonable, and 48% thought they were not. Responses of the participants for the assessment of the research environment in Nepalese universities were mixed. Of the respondents, 32% thought it was poor, 33% thought it was fair, 25% thought it was good, and 10% thought it was very good.

In terms of curriculum updates, 42% reported that they occurred occasionally, while 38% believed they happened rarely. A smaller 10% indicated that curriculum updates were frequent. The opinions of the respondents on library resources revealed that 56% considered them adequate to some extent, while 40% believed they were not adequately equipped to support academic and research activities.

Comparison of commitment to teaching profession according to place of residence

The results of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the scale of teachers' commitment to teaching profession and

Table 8: Comparison of Commitment to Teaching Profession According to Gender

Scale	Gender	f	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Commitment to Profession	Female	122	4.42	0.39	242	1.248	.213
	Male	122	4.32	0.57			
Commitment to Students	Female	122	4.24	.47	242	1.016	.310
	Male	122	4.17	.68			
Selfless Work	Female	122	4.46	.42	242	1.658	.099
	Male	122	4.34	.67			
Total (Commitment to Profession)	Female	122	4.40	.40	242	1.569	.118
	Male	122	4.30	.61			

Table 9: ANOVA Results of Commitment to Teaching Profession Scale and Its Subscales According to Place of Residence

Source of Variance	Gender	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F Values	P
Commitment to Profession	Between Groups	.932	2	.466	1.129	.325
	In-groups	98.601	39	.413		
	Total	99.532	41			
Commitment to Students	Between Groups	.923	2	.461	1.329	.267
	In-groups	83.006	39	.347		
	Total	83.928	41			
Selfless Work	Between Groups	1.224	2	.612	1.946	.145
	In-groups	75.180	39	.315		
	Total	76.404	41			
Total (Commitment to Profession)	Between Groups	.792	2	.396	1.473	.231
	In-groups	64.268	39	.269		
	Total	65.061	41			

its sub-dimensions according to the variable of settlement are presented in Table 9.

Table 9 shows the ANOVA results of teachers' level of dedication to the profession according to all scale items and sub-dimensions of the scale according to the place of residence. When the ANOVA test results related to the settlements for the whole scale are examined, it is seen that there are no statistically significant differences in the comparison of the level of dedication to the profession and the settlement ($f(2-239)=1.473$; $p = .231 > .05$).

Looking at the sub-dimensions of the teachers' dedication to the profession scale; According to the ANOVA test analysis result applied for the sub-dimension of dedication to the profession, no significant difference was observed between the place of residence and the sub-dimension of dedication to the profession ($f(2-239)=1.129$; $p=.325 > .05$). According to the results of the ANOVA test analysis applied for the students sub-dimension,

According to this information, teachers' level of dedication to the profession and its sub-dimensions do not change according to the settlement. This shows that teachers working in different settlements have similar levels of commitment to their profession.

Comparison of Commitment to Teaching Profession According to the Type of Graduated Faculty

The results of the independent samples t-test conducted to determine whether teachers' professional commitment and its sub-dimensions show significant differences according to the type of faculty graduated are shown in Table 10.

When Table 10 is examined, it is seen that there are no statistically significant differences in the mean scores of the faculty of graduation according to the results of the independent samples t-test applied to compare the professional dedication of teachers who graduated from the faculty of education and other faculties ($t(229)=-1.129$; $p>.05$).

Table 10: T-Test Results of Commitment to Teaching Profession Scale and Its Subscales According to Graduated Faculty Type

Scale	Faculty Type	f	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Commitment to Profession	Faculty of Education	155	4.32	.68	229	-1.248	.213
	Other faculties	76	4.43	.56			
Commitment to Students	Faculty of Education	155	4.16	.62	229	-.667	.506
	Other faculties	76	4.21	.51			
Selfless Work	Faculty of Education	155	4.35	.60	229	-1.186	.237
	Other faculties	76	4.45	.47			
Total (Commitment to Profession)	Faculty of Education	155	4.30	.56	298	-1.229	.195
	Other faculties	76	4.40	.43			

no significant difference was observed between the place of residence and the selflessness sub-dimension ($f(2-239)=1.329$; $p=.267 > .05$). According to the ANOVA test analysis result for the selfless work dimension, there was no significant difference between the place of residence and the sub-dimension of dedication to students ($f(2-239)=1.946$; $p=.145 > .05$).

When the results of the sub-dimensions of the scale are examined, it is seen that the mean scores of the sub-dimensions of Dedication to Profession ($t(229)=-1.248$; $p=.213 > .05$), Dedication to Students ($t(229)=-.667$; $p=.506 > .05$) and Selfless Work ($t(229)=-1.229$; $p=.237 > .05$) do not show a significant difference according to the faculty of graduation.

Comparison of commitment to teaching profession according to the type of school

The results of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the teachers' commitment to teaching profession scale and its sub-dimensions according to the type of school they work in are shown in Table 11.

commitment ($f(6-236)=.667$; $p=.669>.05$). According to the results of the ANOVA test analysis applied for the students sub-dimension, no significant difference was observed between the type of settlement and the sub-dimension of dedication to students ($f(6-236)=.300$; $p=.937>.05$). According to the results of the ANOVA test analysis applied for the dimension of selfless work, no significant difference was observed between the place of residence and the sub-dimension of dedication to

Table 11: One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Results of Commitment to Teaching Profession Scale and its Subscales According to the Type of School

Source of Variance	Gender	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F Values	P
Commitment to Profession	Between Groups	1.708	6	.285	.667	.669
	In-groups	99.310	36	.421		
	Total	101.018	42			
Commitment to Students	Between Groups	.643	6	.107	.300	.937
	In-groups	84.374	36	.358		
	Total	85.017	42			
Selfless Work	Between Groups	2.191	6	.365	1.157	.330
	In-groups	74.471	36	.316		
	Total	76.663	42			
Total (Commitment to Profession)	Between Groups	1.046	6	.174	.663	.704
	In-groups	65	36	.275		
	Total	66.046	42	.285		

In table 11, ANOVA results are given for teachers' professional commitment and sub-dimensions of the scale according to the type of school they work in. When the ANOVA test results related to the types of schools where teachers work for the whole scale are examined, it is seen that there are no statistically significant differences in the comparison of the level of dedication to the profession and the place of duty ($f(6-236)=.663$; $p=.704>.05$).

students ($f(6-236)=1.157$; $p=.330>.05$).

Looking at the sub-dimensions of teachers' professional commitment scale; according to the ANOVA test analysis result applied for the sub-dimension of professional commitment, no significant difference was observed between the type of school and the sub-dimension of professional

Comparison of commitment to the teaching profession according to having a counselor/reader teacher in the first year of starting the profession

The results of the independent samples t-test conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the scale of teachers' commitment to teaching profession and its sub-dimensions according to having a counselor/mentor teacher in the first year of the profession are shown in Table 12.

When Table 12 is examined, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the dedication to the profession of those who have and those who do not have

Table 12: T-test Results of Commitment to the Teaching Profession Scale and its Subscales According to Having a Counselor/Reader Teacher in the First Year of Employment

Scale		f	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Commitment to Profession	Yes	160	4.40	.64	235	.897	.371
	No	77	4.32	.63			
Commitment to Students	Yes	160	4.21	.62	235	.219	.827
	No	77	4.19	.52			
Selfless Work	Yes	160	4.38	.58	235	-.852	.395
	No	77	4.45	.53			
Total (Commitment to Profession)	Yes	160	4.36	.53	235	.120	.905
	No	77	4.35	.49			

dedication to the profession after the t-test conducted to compare the teachers' dedication to the profession according to the variable of having a guidance/counselor teacher in the first year they started their profession ($t_{(235)}=.120$; $p=.905>.05$).

When the results of the sub-dimensions of the scale are examined, it is seen that the mean scores of the sub-dimensions of dedication to the profession ($t_{(235)}=.897$; $p=.371>.05$), dedication to students ($t_{(235)}=-.219$; $p=.827>.05$) and selfless work ($t_{(235)}=-.852$; $p=.395>.05$) do not create a significant difference according to the status of having a guidance/counselor teacher in the first year of their profession.

DISCUSSION

According to the results of the study, it was observed that teachers' professional commitment was high in the overall scale and in all sub-dimensions. These results are in parallel with the results of other studies in the literature. It was determined that these studies had high levels of professional commitment (Kırbaç & Kaya, 2023; Özel, Kaya, Ekinci, & Yılmaz, 2023; Kozikoğlu & Özcanlı, 2020; Turhan, Demirli, & Nazik, 2012) and supported this study. Saks, Soosaar, and Ilves (2016) concluded in their study with students that students value their teachers highly. In the context of these results, it is undeniable that teaching is a profession that requires commitment to the profession. In order to realize a quality education in educational institutions, there is a need for dedicated teachers who are committed to their profession (Seferoğlu, 2004).

It was seen that teachers' level of commitment to the profession did not differ in the sub-dimensions of commitment to the profession, commitment to students and selfless work and in the total score of the scale (commitment to the profession) according to the gender variable. There are studies in the literature that support this study. The results of the studies conducted by Turhan, Demirli, and Nazik (2012), Bozdaş (2013), and Örer (2020) did not find a difference in terms of gender, which is consistent with the results of this study. This situation can be interpreted as being male or female does not have a significant effect on professional commitment. On the other hand, there are also studies in the literature that show a significant difference according to the gender variable that is not consistent with this study (Güner, 2006; Karagöz, 2008; Kandemir, 2009; Altunay, 2017; Kozikoğlu & Özcanlı, 2020). In the context of these results, it can be interpreted that being male or female may show differences in terms of professional commitment in some cases.

It was observed that teachers' level of commitment to the profession did not differ in the sub-dimensions of commitment to the profession, commitment to students and selfless work and in the total score of the scale (commitment to the profession) according to the branch, the settlement where they work and the type of school they work. In addition, Sarıbaş, Akça, and Meydan (2020) found that there was no difference in the level of commitment to the teaching profession in terms of the variables of place of duty, graduation year and time spent in teaching, while they observed a significant difference in terms

of graduation field and school type. In the study conducted by Kozikoğlu and Özcanlı (2020), it was concluded that teachers' commitment to the profession did not differ in terms of their desire for postgraduate education, school level and branch variable. Özkan (2012) examined the attitudes of prospective teachers towards the teaching profession and concluded that there is a significant difference in terms of interest in the profession, love for the profession and professional commitment according to age and working in a profession, but there is no difference according to the level of education, graduated department and the sector of work. It was determined that there was no significant difference in attitudes towards the reputation of the teaching profession and commitment to the profession according to the sector of employment, while no significant differences were observed in terms of education level, age, employment status and graduated field variables.

It was observed that teachers' commitment to the profession did not differ in the sub-dimensions of commitment to the profession, commitment to students and selfless work and in the total score of the scale (commitment to the profession) according to the status of having a guidance/counselor teacher in the beginning year of the profession. In the study conducted by Kozikoğlu and Senemoğlu (2018), it was concluded that teachers who are new to the profession experience difficulties such as the fact that their mentor teachers are from different branches and that they have difficulties in establishing effective communication due to not being in the same institution. On the other hand, problems related to the planning and implementation of the teaching process, school adaptation and social relations, administrator-parent relations and the physical infrastructure of the school are some of the important difficulties faced by beginning teachers. For this reason, having a mentor teacher in the first years of the profession is important in overcoming the problems to be experienced. In their study, Dağ and Sarı (2017) stated that both pre-service and in-service teachers need a mentor teacher in terms of pedagogy and that the counselor/mentor teacher service should be provided by experienced teachers and should be immediately accessible.

Implications and recommendations

In the study, teachers' professional commitment status was examined in the context of various variables and their professional commitment status was determined. Based on these findings, a suggestion can be made that the concept of professional commitment is important and that teachers should be given the necessary support to bring teachers' professional commitment to higher levels because the teaching profession is a profession that requires commitment. In addition, depending on the fact that the teaching profession does not differ in terms of demographic variables as a result of this research, new studies to be conducted with a different sample group and teachers in a different geographical region may reveal different results. In addition, qualitative research can be conducted to examine teachers' professional commitment in a deeper way. In addition, the relationship between commitment and different variables such as professional motivation, job satisfaction, working conditions, wage scale that may affect the level of commitment to the teaching profession can also be examined.

In particular, the fact that there is no difference between the levels of commitment to the teaching profession of graduates of education faculties and other faculties is an issue that needs to be investigated. Because faculties of education are academic institutions that provide education on the teaching profession and train teachers, and it is expected that graduates from these faculties will have higher levels of commitment to the profession. For this reason, qualitative research can be conducted to investigate in more detail the levels of commitment to the profession of individuals who graduated from faculties of education and other faculties and continue their teaching profession.

In this study, teachers' levels of commitment to the profession were examined. It should also be investigated to what extent the expectations of students and parents are an important factor affecting the level of commitment to the profession, especially when school success is added to these expectations.

Another important issue is that the characteristics of mentor teachers who are assigned to contribute to the development of novice teachers, such as their dedication to the profession, their positive thoughts towards the profession, their level of competence in terms of both pedagogical knowledge and field knowledge, and their socially positive behavior, may have positive / negative effects on the dedication of novice teachers and this situation should be constantly monitored by educational administrators.

Conclusion

In conclusion, teachers who are committed to their profession play a key role in the lives of students. Especially the teacher's passion and motivation for his/her profession is reflected in his/her performance and behavior. This is observed by the students and this positive environment helps students to learn, exhibit positive behaviors and acquire good habits.

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Consent to participate: The participants were informed the process of research report.

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